

**DMITRY ALEKSEYEVICH KABALEVSKY FOUNDER OF SCIENTIFIC
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Abstract: This article discusses the life and beautiful musical works of the great Russian composer D.A. Kabalevsky, as well as his reforms for young people in the field of music.

Key words: School musical education, Russian classical music, composer, conservatory, musical genres.

The basis of the reforms implemented in our country is the educational process and its proper organization. It is not without reason that the issue of education of young people and raising them as a well-rounded person in the process of education is urgent. Also, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan Article 41 states that "Everyone has the right to education." is marked as proof of our opinion.

President Sh. In the works written by Mirziyoyev entitled "Together we will build a free and prosperous democratic state of Uzbekistan", our 1st President I. Karimov "Our children must be stronger, more educated, wiser and, of course, happier than us" the issue of education and training of young people lies in the ground of the thoughts written.

As evidence of our opinion, our President Sh. The fact that the first steps of the 5 initiatives put forward by Mirziyoyev belong to art, i.e. music science, encourages students to study and understand the innovations and reforms implemented in this field. According to the essence of the initiative, attention was also paid to the issue of increasing the number of highly educated personnel in the field of music and art. This automatically created the need to study music and its history.

Studying the history of music not only helps to learn the main stages of development of world music, but also serves to form the basis of musical-theoretical knowledge, helps to deeply understand, comprehensively understand and perceive musical phenomena. Studying the history of music serves to introduce the mature masterpieces of world music art, major figures, genres and forms of instrumental and vocal music, examples of genres, to develop and expand the level of musical worldview, taste and culture. The study of the history of music is integrated in the section of issues related to other types of art (literature, visual arts, sculpture, etc.) along with the issues of art, and has

a complete idea of the universal aesthetic values of artistic culture. helps to In the process of studying the history of music, the major periods of the development of the art of music, advanced achievements, musical styles and genres that appeared and developed in different periods, major schools and their bright creators and representatives, historical and theoretical issues of the art of music are analyzed. will be done. Also, studying the life and works of musicologists and composers who contributed greatly to the development of the art of music is a great spiritual need.

Here is one of such well-known devotees of art, Dmitry Alekseevich Kabalaevsky. He is a well-known composer, teacher, pianist and conductor, musical thinker, public figure, creator of the concept of musical-aesthetic education of children and youth, passionate promoter of the world's classical musical heritage, played a huge role in the formation of the artistic space of Russian culture. His active life and creative position have always attracted interest and recognition not only in Russia, but also beyond its borders, which allows us to talk about the contribution of the master to the world artistic culture as a whole.

D. B. Kabalevsky was born on December 30, 1904 in Saint Petersburg. The composer's childhood was incomparable. Important events happened in those years of his life. The composer's father Kabalevsky Boris Klavdievich was a mathematician in an insurance company, he was a very progressive person, and his mother Nadezhda Aleksandrovna Kabalevskaya was a housewife and she devoted a lot of time to children. He studied at a three-year city school and at the 1st Petrograd Classical Gymnasium. At the age of 11, he graduated from the city school and entered the 1st Petersburg men's gymnasium.

He started his independent work in 1922 (pianist in cinemas, accompanist, secretary and manager of A.N. Skryabin Music College). D. B. Kabalevsky graduated from the Moscow Conservatory with honors. Student of composition of N. Ya. Myaskovsky, graduated in 1929; A. B. Goldenweiser, who graduated in piano in 1930, his name is written on the gold plaque of the conservatory, which includes the names of his most distinguished and distinguished students. From 1925, he first studied at the music college named after A.N. Scriabin (including 1932-1939 - professor in the class of composition), taught at the Moscow Conservatory from 1932 (professor from 1939) ... Over the past years: an accompanist at the Central Children's Theater, an editor at the Radio Committee, editor of the magazine "Soviet Music" He worked as editor (1940-1947), founder and editor-in-chief of "Music in School" magazine (1983-1987), head of art

broadcasting department. During the war, he taught at the conservatory in Sverdlovsk, went to the South-Western Front (1942) and Leningrad (1943). After the war, he visited Austria, Australia, England, Belgium, Bulgaria, Hungary, East Germany, Canada, China, Mexico, Poland, Romania, USA, Finland, France, Germany, Czechoslovakia, promoting the achievements of Russian music to the whole world. he did Since 1972, D. B. Kabalevsky has been the honorary president of ISME (International Society of Music Education under UNESCO). He was elected an honorary professor of the conservatory in Mexico City (Mexico, 1959), an honorary correspondent member of the Berlin Academy of Arts (GDR, 1969). was a member.

Composer D. B. Kabalevsky's work is distinguished by the development of the traditions of the deep Russian classical music school. His creative legacy is a huge artistic world that serves as an example for our contemporaries to realize the artist's self-realization, embodying his moral and aesthetic ideals. Kabalevsky's compositional heritage is extremely extensive: five operas, ballets, operettas, thirteen symphonic works, seven concertos, six oratorios and cantatas, many chamber works, for children and young people, as well as many for master musicians. created piano pieces. He wrote hundreds of songs, vocal cycles, music for theater and radio shows, as well as music for ten films. At the same time, the most important features of human personality can be clearly seen in Kabalevsky's early works. In his works, one can feel the depth and clarity of creative perception, an inseparable connection with the surrounding life.

There is no doubt that Kabalevsky connected his work with musical education, children and young people and dedicated many of his works to them. As a scientist and teacher (candidate since 1935, doctor of arts since 1965, full member of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences since 1971), he developed a unique worldwide system of introducing children to musical culture. He convinced educational leaders to include music education as a subject in the curriculum, and his initiative was of great importance in raising the level of music culture in the country. In 1964, music clubs began to be held in the halls of the Union House, and this was the largest cultural project of that time aimed at the development of children's musical education. D. B. Kabalevsky attracted famous musicians, composers, and teachers to it. For example, T. Khrennikov, N. Sats, Ya. Flier, V. Dudarova, G. Rozdestvensky, and others, also selected potential school teachers and entrusted them with a number of tasks. The composer conducted extensive correspondence with children, partially published in the book "My dear friends" and other publications. He believed that it was necessary

not only to hold large events for thousands of schoolchildren, but also to communicate with young people individually and help them.

His name is associated with young people all over the world. Most of the more than 400 works were created for children and young people. The goal of Kabalevsky's whole life was to become a teacher. There is no school or pioneer camp, creative house or music studio without his music and especially his songs. For many years, his face did not leave the TV screen, his voice was heard on the radio.

The name of Dmitry Borisovich Kabalevsky is known in every family, he brought joy to people and taught them to rejoice. He sincerely believed that "In our future, children will stop crying and laugh, of course, loudly...".

In conclusion, we can say that the talent of D. B. Kabalevsky is very versatile. From the above story about the work of the composer, it can be seen how great devotee of music and art he is. He happily gave his knowledge and talent to the youth and society. An accomplished conductor and pianist, he performed in concerts, helped amateur groups, and published articles as a public figure and music critic. School music education was reformed on his initiative. Many of his works are still widely used in the field of music pedagogy. He became one of the founders of the famous Tchaikovsky music competition and composed the tunes to be performed by the contestants.

We, the young generation, want to have more such devotees of art, and of course we want to leave a bright mark like them.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T. 2016
2. Sh. Mirziyoyev. "We will build a free and prosperous democratic country of Uzbekistan together" T.: "Uzbekistan" 2016
3. Sh. Mirziyoyev. "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people." T.: Uzbekistan. 2017
4. G. Tursunova, R. Tursunova. "History of world music". Study guide. 2017
5. A.H. Trigulova. "Foreign music literature". T.: knowledge. 2019
6. N. Sharipov. "Foreign music literature". Study guide. T.: 2014
7. B.V. Levik. "History of foreign music". Moscow.: 1980.
8. I.A. Akbarov. "Dictionary of Music". T.: G'.G'. Literary and Art Publishing House named after 1987
9. A. Panfilov. "Velikiye Composer" N 78. Kyiv. 2006
10. A.I. Kandinsky, E.M. Orlova. "Russian musical literature". SPb. 1972

